

Dangers of ICTs

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Introduction

In today’s world, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a ubiquitous component of our life. ICT can be defined as “anything which allows us to get information, to communicate with each other, or to have an effect on the environment using electronic or digital equipment”

ICT includes desktop computers, laptops, iPads, digital video cameras, telephones, fax machines, mobile/smart phones, tape recorders, computer games, programmable toys, video conferencing technologies and closed-circuit television, data projectors and electronic whiteboards.

Child abuse

The **World Health Organization (WHO)** defines **child abuse and child maltreatment** as “All forms of physical and/or emotional ill-treatment, sexual abuse, neglect or negligent treatment or commercial or other exploitation, resulting in actual or potential harm to the child’s health, survival, development or dignity in the context of a relationship of responsibility, trust or power.”

This may include any act or failure to act by a parent or other caregiver that results in actual or potential harm to a child, and can occur in a child’s home, or in the organizations, schools or communities the child interacts with.

Online Child abuse

Online child abuse is a unique form of child abuse also known as “Cyber Molestation” due to its virtual, distanced, and anonymous nature. Such abuse may not happen face-to-face, nor does it necessarily require physical contact. Online abuse is any type of abuse that happens on the web, whether through social networks, playing online games or using mobile phones. Children can be at risk of online abuse from people they know, as well as from strangers. Online abuse may be part of abuse that is taking place in the real world (for example bullying or grooming), or it may be that the abuse only happens online (for example persuading children to take part in sexual activity online). Children can feel like there is no escape from online abuse – abusers can contact them at any time of the day or night.

Neglect and Its Types

Neglect is the ongoing failure to meet a child’s basic needs and is the most common form of child abuse. A child may be put in danger or not protected from physical or emotional harm. They may not get the love, care and attention they need from their parents. A child who’s neglected will often suffer from other abuse as well. Neglect is dangerous and can cause serious, long-term damage - even death. This includes-Physical neglect, Educational neglect, Emotional neglect and Medical neglect.

Background on Online Child abuse

Children have increased access to ICTs and in recent decades, have tended to adopt these technologies from an early age and hence it is fully embedded in their lives. This context facilitates opportunities for the misuse of ICTs to abuse and exploit children. Children can easily engage with strangers and exchange large data files, while the possibilities for parental supervision and monitoring are restricted. Children are also at particular risk as they often do not fully understand threats associated with the use of ICTs, or they are not sufficiently aware that, once shared, control over such material is effectively waived.

Types of Online Child abuse

1. Bullying online or Cyber bullying
2. Online Grooming
3. Child sexual abuse online
4. Live Streaming
5. Gifting for gaming

Bullying online or cyberbullying

Cyberbullying is an increasingly common form of bullying behaviour which happens on social networks, games and mobile phones. Children may know who is bullying them online or they may be targeted by someone using a fake or anonymous account. It is easy to be anonymous online and this may increase the likelihood of engaging in bullying behaviour.

Cyberbullying includes

- sending threatening or abusive text messages
- creating and sharing embarrassing images or videos
- ‘trolling’ - the sending of menacing or upsetting messages on social networks, chat rooms or online games
- setting up hate sites or groups about a particular child
- encouraging young people to self-harm
- creating fake accounts, hijacking or stealing online identities to embarrass a young person or cause trouble using their name
- pressuring children into sending sexual images or engaging in sexual conversations.

Online Grooming

Grooming is when someone builds an emotional connection with a child to gain their trust for sexual abuse, sexual exploitation or trafficking.

- Groomers may be male or female. They could be of any age or pretends like a child.
- Groomers can use social media sites, instant messaging apps including teen dating apps, or online gaming platforms to connect with a young person or child.

- They can spend time learning about a young person’s interests from their online profiles and then use this knowledge to help them build up a relationship.
- Groomers do not always target one particular child. Sometimes they will send messages to hundreds of young people and wait to see who responds.

Child sexual abuse online

When sexual exploitation happens online, young people may be persuaded or forced, to:

- send or post sexually explicit images of themselves
- take part in sexual activities via a webcam or smartphone
- have sexual conversations by text or online.
- Images or videos may continue to be shared long after the sexual abuse has stopped.

Live Streaming is ‘in the moment’

Children and young people often do things in the heat of the moment and act on impulse without thinking of the consequences – just like offline. For example, they may share personal information when asked or do things that in another situation they wouldn’t do, such as share something private or even sexual. A study of Thinkuknowyoutube channel has shown that children often do not see live streaming as something tangible and so they may share things that they wouldn’t share via a photo or pre-recorded video.

Gifting for Gaming

Offenders can give ‘gifts’ via gaming platforms. Children do not have access to money to make purchases in games, so offenders use gifts in gaming to encourage children to trust them. They may offer gifts asking for nothing in return, this can be part of the grooming process. Later they persuade children taking a photo of themselves.

Few examples on Online child abuse happened in India

The risk for Indian kids being cyberbullied has increased over the years. According to available data, India ranks much higher when it comes to cyberbullying, in comparison to other Asian countries. Studies have highlighted that 53% of the Indian kids in the age group of 8-17 have been subjected to cyberbullying at least once.

- A Class V student approached for a fake Facebook profile created to defame him.
- A Class VIII girl’s Facebook account was hacked for personal vendetta.
- New threats like the **Blue Whale Challenge** and **Pub-G**

Parents neglecting children by giving Tablets and Smart phones

Tablets and smartphones are great gadgets for making kids busy and quiet, especially for harassed parents who has more urgent things to do than attending to their kids. They use it to make kids sit quietly in a car ride, meal time or even go into the potty.

Bad Effects of Tablets and Smart Phones

- During the child’s first years, his brain develops rapidly, and very young children learn best by interacting with people, not screens. Being head down and having no eye contact with people might be harmful to their brain development.
- Screens distract one or two-year-olds from interacting with parents, siblings and other kids. Dan Siegel of Mindful Awareness Research Center as well as a study by UCLA’s Children’s Digital Media Center (2014) thinks this may impede language, social and emotional development. It may affect children’s development of insights, empathy, ways of knowing themselves, and connecting with relationships.

- Also, toddlers need to be active physically. They should be actively exploring their environment, and not sedentary, getting almost all of stimulations from screen, and not building their bodies through physical play. This is why the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) do not recommend screen time for kids younger than 2.
- The American Heart Association expert panel suggests that screen time could contribute to a child’s future heart disease. Spending too much time with screens makes a child sedentary, which is associated with being overweight and obese. Obesity tends to continue into adulthood, and is a risk factor for high cholesterol, high blood pressure, and a variety of serious diseases.
- Doctors have a point on attention span and concentration, as well as appetite control.
- According to Catherine Steiner-Adair, a Harvard-affiliated clinical psychologist, “children need time to daydream, deal with anxieties, process their thoughts and share them with parents, who can provide reassurance”, which does not happen with ICT
- Children who sleep near a smartphone average 20.6 fewer minutes of sleep every night. This may be caused by the high levels of blue light emitted by the screens which deplete melatonin, a hormone linked to circadian rhythm. The extra screen time at night are resetting their bodies’ clocks in a way that makes it difficult for them to sleep, especially in their early stages of puberty. This results in lack of sleep and insufficient rest.
- The American Academy of Ophthalmology says that blue light could damage the retina of the eye, makes it harder to fall asleep and causes dry eyes.
- Results from the 2018 National Institute of Health study showed that screen time may be affecting the structure of the brains and thinning of the brain’s cortex.
- Teens who spend too much time playing computer games with violent content - having problems with violent and aggressive behaviour, according to studies reported by the Palo Alto Medical Foundation.

Conclusion

Impacts of prolonged use of ICT on child’s development:

- Children become addicted to new technologies.
- Influences their peer-groups to do so.
- Children are not getting enough sleep, exercise and other play activities.
- Lack of educational motivation and learning curiosity.
- Bad Academic Performance and hence academic malpractice.
- Musculoskeletal problems
- Vision problems
- Lack of proper cognitive developments
- Psychological depression which mainly shows social-phobia
- ADHD issues getting continued to adolescent period.
- Develop aggressive behaviours compared to previous generation children

Few recommendations for parents

- Children who use smartphones and other devices in their free time for less than two hours a day, at least an hour of physical activity, 9-10 hours of sleep, performed better on cognitive tests assessing their thinking, language and memory, according to a 2018 study published in the Lancet Child & Adolescent Health.
- When your child talks on the phone, be alert how and what he is responding.
- Restrict your child from taking phones to the school and other travelling time.

- Play alongside your children and interact with them face-to-face.
- Encourage family meals, chit-chats and other socializing activities.
- Look for quality apps that promote building vocabulary, mathematical, literacy, and science concepts.
- Keep smartphones out of the bedrooms.
- Make the children know about their own values.

Educate them about the following points

- Do not reply to abusive messages that may only encourage the bully.
- Keep a record of events/messages or pictures, you will need them for the police or the ISP, or mobile phone company to trace the bully.
- Users and phone numbers can often be blocked.
- Think before you send pictures of someone via email, or mobile phone, they can spread far beyond your circle of friends.
- If you receive a rude image or text about someone else do not forward it, you could be assisting a bully or breaking the law.
- You have a right not to be harassed or bullied online, make sure you tell an adult
- If you are worried about a child or need advice or to report, call on 0808 800 5000 - National Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Children(NSPCC) 24x7 helpline.
- Each of us has a responsibility to keep childhood free from abuse, and we must do everything possible to protect children and prevent it before happening.

Web Sources

1. <http://journalcra.com/article/ict-development-india-current-scenario>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Child_abuse
3. <https://www.nspcc.org.uk/preventing-abuse/child-abuse-and-neglect/online-abuse/>
4. <https://www.facebook.com/crimeagainsthumanity786/>
5. <https://www.dorset.police.uk/help-advice-crime-prevention/abuse-exploitation-neglect/child-abuse/child-neglect/>
6. https://www.unodc.org/documents/Cybercrime/Study_on_the_Effects.pdf
7. <https://www.raisesmartkid.com/all-ages/1-articles/smartphone-and-tablet-screen-time-good-or-bad-for-kids>
8. <https://www.livestrong.com/article/48504-negative-effects-computer-games-children/>
9. <https://psychcentral.com/lib/how-do-smartphones-affect-childhood-psychology/>
10. http://lincolnshirescb.proceduresonline.com/chapters/p_child_abuse_ict.htm